

POZNAN UNIVERSITY OF MEDICAL SCIENCES

BIOETHICS COMMITTEE

no. 70, Bukowska Str.
60-812, Poznań
Poland

Phone: + 48 61 854 73 36
e-mail: bioetyka.ump@ump.edu.pl
[www. bioetyka.ump.edu.pl](http://www.bioetyka.ump.edu.pl)

Poznań, January 10, 2024r.

KB – 33/24

CONFIRMATION

I hereby confirm that the scientific research entitled:

***„Effects of spherical and rod-like gold nanoparticles on
the reactivity of human peripheral blood leukocytes ”***

conducted by:

Patrycja Talarska-Markiewicz

is a non-experimental study.

According to the Polish law and GCP regulations
this research does not require approval of the Bioethics Committee
at Poznan University of Medical Sciences.

M. Krawczyński

Chairman of the Committee

Professor Maciej Krawczyński, MD, PhD